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1

Preliminaries

1.1 Domain Adaptation

Domain adaptation (DA) aims to transfer knowledge from a labeled source domain to an unlabeled or sparsely labeled target domain whose data distribution differs from the source. Formally, let $\mathcal{D}_s = \{(x_s, y_s)\}$ and $\mathcal{D}_t = \{(x_t, y_t)\}$ denote the source and target domains with marginal distributions $p_s(x)$ and $p_t(x)$, respectively. Since $p_s(x) \neq p_t(x)$, models trained solely on \mathcal{D}_s often suffer severe performance degradation when applied to \mathcal{D}_t . Domain adaptation addresses this issue by learning domain-invariant feature representations that minimize the distribution shift across domains [36].

Specifically, it seeks to learn a feature mapping $f_\theta(x)$ such that the feature distributions of the two domains are aligned, i.e., $p_s(f_\theta(x)) \approx p_t(f_\theta(x))$, to ensure generalization on the target domain [17]. In standard domain adaptation, it is typically assumed that the source and target share the same label space, i.e., $\mathcal{Y}_S = \mathcal{Y}_T$, but have different marginal input distributions. Learning such a domain-invariant mapping encourages the model to capture domain-invariant semantics shared across domains while discarding domain-specific variations. When the transformed representations $z = f_\theta(x)$ from both domains follow a similar distribution, the classifier/regressor h_ϕ trained on the labeled source features can make reliable predictions on the target features as well. Consequently, aligning $p_s(f_\theta(x))$ and $p_t(f_\theta(x))$ bridges the gap between the source and target domains at the representation level, enabling effective knowledge transfer and improving robustness and

generalization under distribution shift.

To achieve alignment, most DA methods optimize the following joint objective:

$$\min_{\theta, \phi} \mathbb{E}_{(x_s, y_s) \sim \mathcal{D}_S} [\ell(h_\phi(f_\theta(x_s)), y_s)] + \lambda \text{Disc}(P_S^z, P_T^z), \quad z = f_\theta(x), \quad (1.1)$$

where the first term minimizes the supervised loss on the labeled source domain, and the second term enforces alignment between the source and target feature distributions. $\text{Disc}(\cdot, \cdot)$ denotes a discrepancy measure such as Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) [7, 17], CORAL distance [26, 27], Wasserstein distance [3], or an adversarial loss [6].

While classical DA assumes a shared label space between source and target, this constraint is often unrealistic in practice. **Universal Domain Adaptation (UniDA)** extends DA to the setting where the label spaces partially overlap. That is, some labels may be shared between the source and target ($\mathcal{Y}_S \cap \mathcal{Y}_T$), while others exist only in one domain, leading to a partially overlapping label space (i.e., $\mathcal{Y}_S \cap \mathcal{Y}_T \subset \mathcal{Y}_S \cup \mathcal{Y}_T$). The key challenge lies in automatically identifying samples belonging to the shared label space and aligning their features, while preventing negative transfer from source-only or target-only labels. Representative UniDA approaches include uncertainty-based transferability estimation [32], self-supervised clustering [25], ensemble-based uncertainty calibration [5], and threshold-free optimal transport alignment [1]. Existing UniDA research has focused primarily on classification tasks, whereas regression tasks remain unexplored.

1.2 Gaussian Processes

1.2.1 Standard Gaussian Processes

We provide a brief overview of standard Gaussian processes, mainly following the content in [23, 20]. A Gaussian process (GP) is a collection of random variables $\{f(x)\}_{x \in \mathcal{X}}$ indexed by a continuous domain $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$, such that any finite subset follows a joint Gaussian distribution. A GP is completely specified by a mean function $m : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and a positive semi-definite covariance function $k : \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$:

$$f \sim \mathcal{GP}(m(\cdot), k(\cdot, \cdot)), \quad m(x) = \mathbb{E}[f(x)], \quad k(x, x') = \text{Cov}(f(x), f(x')). \quad (1.2)$$

In this section, we regard $k(\cdot, \cdot)$ as a given covariance function and do not discuss its specific forms. In practice, $m(x)$ is often set to a constant (e.g., $m(x) \equiv 0$), and any global offset can be absorbed by centering the responses or by learning a mean parameter jointly with the covariance.

Regression model. Given training inputs $X = \{x_i\}_{i=1}^n \subset \mathcal{X}$ and noisy observations

$$y_i = f(x_i) + \varepsilon_i, \quad \varepsilon_i \stackrel{\text{i.i.d.}}{\sim} \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2), \quad (1.3)$$

let

$$\mathbf{y} = [y_1, \dots, y_n]^\top, \quad m_X = [m(x_1), \dots, m(x_n)]^\top, \quad K_{XX} = [k(x_i, x_j)]_{i,j=1}^n \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}. \quad (1.4)$$

Then the observations follow a multivariate normal distribution:

$$\mathbf{y} \sim \mathcal{N}(m_X, K_{XX} + \sigma^2 I_n). \quad (1.5)$$

Posterior prediction. For test inputs $X_* = \{x_j^*\}_{j=1}^m \subset \mathcal{X}$, define

$$\begin{aligned} m_{X_*} &= [m(x_1^*), \dots, m(x_m^*)]^\top, & K_{XX_*} &= [k(x_i, x_j^*)]_{i=1..n, j=1..m} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}, \\ K_{X_*X_*} &= [k(x_i^*, x_j^*)]_{i,j=1}^m \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.6)$$

Because the joint prior over \mathbf{y} and the latent function values $f_* = [f(x_1^*), \dots, f(x_m^*)]^\top$ is Gaussian, the posterior predictive distribution of f_* is:

$$f_* \mid X, \mathbf{y}, X_* \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_*, \Sigma_*), \quad (1.7)$$

where

$$\mu_* = m_{X_*} + K_{X_*X_*}^\top (K_{XX} + \sigma^2 I_n)^{-1} (\mathbf{y} - m_X), \quad (1.8)$$

$$\Sigma_* = K_{X_*X_*} - K_{X_*X_*}^\top (K_{XX} + \sigma^2 I_n)^{-1} K_{X_*X_*}. \quad (1.9)$$

The predictive distribution for the **noisy observations** $y_* = f_* + \varepsilon_*$ is $\mathcal{N}(\mu_*, \Sigma_* + \sigma^2 I_m)$ (with $\varepsilon_* \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2 I_m)$ independent of f_*).

Marginal likelihood and hyperparameter optimization. Let θ denote all hyperparameters (e.g., kernel parameters, noise variance σ^2 , and mean function parameters). The log marginal likelihood has the closed form:

$$\log p(\mathbf{y} \mid X, \theta) = -\frac{1}{2} (\mathbf{y} - m_X)^\top (K_{XX} + \sigma^2 I_n)^{-1} (\mathbf{y} - m_X) - \frac{1}{2} \log |K_{XX} + \sigma^2 I_n| - \frac{n}{2} \log(2\pi). \quad (1.10)$$

This expression consists of three interpretable terms: the first measures data fidelity (negative Mahalanobis distance), the second penalizes model complexity (through the covariance determinant), and the third is a normalization constant. Maximizing (1.10) provides a principled approach to learning θ that automatically balances data fitting with

model complexity [20].

Computational aspects. Exact GP inference requires solving linear systems involving $K_{XX} + \sigma^2 I_n$. The dominant cost is the Cholesky factorization $LL^\top = K_{XX} + \sigma^2 I_n$, which requires $O(n^3)$ time and $O(n^2)$ memory. After the Cholesky factorization, the predictive mean for m test points costs $O(nm)$, the diagonal of the predictive covariance costs $O(n^2m)$, and the full predictive covariance costs $O(n^2m + nm^2)$ [23, 20].

1.2.2 Stochastic Variational Gaussian Processes (SVGP)

To overcome the computational limitations described above, Stochastic Variational Gaussian Processes (SVGP) [28, 9] propose a sparse variational formulation that reduces the computational complexity while preserving the nonparametric nature of Gaussian processes. For clarity of notation, we denote the full dataset size by N in this section. SVGP maintains the prior $f \sim \mathcal{GP}(m(\cdot), k(\cdot, \cdot))$ but introduces $M \ll N$ inducing variables to decouple computations from the full dataset size. For regression with homoscedastic Gaussian noise,

$$\mathbf{y} \mid \mathbf{f} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{f}, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I}), \quad \mathbf{f} := [f(x_1), \dots, f(x_N)]^\top, \quad (1.11)$$

SVGP achieves scalability through variational inference.

Inducing variables and variational family Choose M inducing inputs $\mathbf{Z} = [z_1, \dots, z_M]^\top$ and define $\mathbf{u} := f(\mathbf{Z})$ with prior

$$p(\mathbf{u}) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{K}_{ZZ}), \quad (\mathbf{K}_{ZZ})_{ij} = k(z_i, z_j), \quad (1.12)$$

where the inducing inputs \mathbf{Z} are treated as learnable parameters (often initialized by k -means).

By joint Gaussianity, $p(\mathbf{f}, \mathbf{u}) = p(\mathbf{f} \mid \mathbf{u}) p(\mathbf{u})$, where

$$p(\mathbf{f} \mid \mathbf{u}) = \mathcal{N}\left(\mathbf{K}_{XZ} \mathbf{K}_{ZZ}^{-1} \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{K}_{XX} - \mathbf{K}_{XZ} \mathbf{K}_{ZZ}^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{ZX}\right), \quad (1.13)$$

and $(\mathbf{K}_{XZ})_{ij} = k(x_i, z_j)$. SVGP posits a variational posterior

$$q(\mathbf{u}) = \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{m}, \mathbf{S}), \quad q(\mathbf{f}) = \int p(\mathbf{f} \mid \mathbf{u}) q(\mathbf{u}) d\mathbf{u}, \quad (1.14)$$

which yields, for each data point x_n , the univariate marginal (the joint $q(\mathbf{f})$ remains a

correlated Gaussian):

$$\begin{aligned} q(f_n) &= \mathcal{N}(\mu_n, \sigma_n^2), \quad \mu_n = \mathbf{k}_{x_n Z} \mathbf{K}_{ZZ}^{-1} \mathbf{m}, \\ \sigma_n^2 &= k(x_n, x_n) - \mathbf{k}_{x_n Z} \mathbf{K}_{ZZ}^{-1} \mathbf{k}_{x_n Z}^\top + \mathbf{k}_{x_n Z} \mathbf{K}_{ZZ}^{-1} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{K}_{ZZ}^{-1} \mathbf{k}_{x_n Z}^\top, \end{aligned} \quad (1.15)$$

where $\mathbf{k}_{x_n Z} = [k(x_n, z_1), \dots, k(x_n, z_M)] \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times M}$.

Evidence lower bound (ELBO) The variational objective is the ELBO

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_{n=1}^N \mathbb{E}_{q(f_n)} [\log p(y_n | f_n)] - \text{KL}(q(\mathbf{u}) \| p(\mathbf{u})). \quad (1.16)$$

For Gaussian likelihood, the expectation is analytic; for non-Gaussian likelihoods (e.g., Bernoulli, Poisson, softmax), it is typically approximated using Gauss–Hermite quadrature (for small M), Laplace approximation, or Monte Carlo integration with reparameterization gradients. With a mini-batch \mathcal{B} , an unbiased estimator is

$$\hat{\mathcal{L}} = \frac{N}{|\mathcal{B}|} \sum_{n \in \mathcal{B}} \mathbb{E}_{q(f_n)} [\log p(y_n | f_n)] - \text{KL}(q(\mathbf{u}) \| p(\mathbf{u})), \quad (1.17)$$

optimized over $\{\mathbf{Z}, \mathbf{m}, \mathbf{S}, \theta, \sigma^2\}$, where θ are kernel hyperparameters.

Prediction For a test input x_* ,

$$p(f_* | x_*, \mathcal{D}) \approx \mathcal{N}(\mu_*, \sigma_*^2), \quad \mu_* = \mathbf{k}_{*Z} \mathbf{K}_{ZZ}^{-1} \mathbf{m}, \quad (1.18)$$

$$\sigma_*^2 = k(x_*, x_*) - \mathbf{k}_{*Z} \mathbf{K}_{ZZ}^{-1} \mathbf{k}_{*Z}^\top + \mathbf{k}_{*Z} \mathbf{K}_{ZZ}^{-1} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{K}_{ZZ}^{-1} \mathbf{k}_{*Z}^\top. \quad (1.19)$$

For observation prediction, add the noise variance σ^2 .

Complexity and scalability Optimization requires solving linear systems involving \mathbf{K}_{ZZ} , dominated by a Cholesky decomposition costing $O(M^3)$. Evaluating the ELBO for N data points costs $O(NM^2)$. Choosing $M \ll N$ (typically 10^2 – 10^3) reduces the dominant cost of exact GPs from $O(N^3)$ to $O(NM^2)$, enabling application to large datasets.

1.3 Optimal Transport

This section introduces discrete, balanced optimal transport (OT), which serves as the fundamental matching objective. Its entropy-regularized variant is further adopted to enhance computational scalability. When the ground cost is induced by a metric d , i.e., $C_{p,q} = d(x_p, y_q)^p$, the optimal value corresponds to the p -Wasserstein distance. The

analysis in this work focuses on the case $p = 1$. For notational consistency with later sections, the OT objective and its entropy-regularized counterpart are denoted by W_1 and $W_{1,\varepsilon}$, respectively. All notations follow standard OT conventions [22].

Setup and notation. Let $a \in \Delta^n$ and $b \in \Delta^m$ be source and target probability vectors, where $\Delta^k := \{x \in \mathbb{R}_+^k : \mathbf{1}^\top x = 1\}$. Let $C \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{n \times m}$ be the nonnegative cost matrix with entries $C_{p,q}$, and let $T \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}^{n \times m}$ be the transport plan with entries $T_{p,q}$.

Standard OT (1-Wasserstein Distance).

$$W_1 = \min_T \sum_{p=1}^n \sum_{q=1}^m C_{p,q} T_{p,q} \quad (1.20)$$

$$\text{s.t. } T_{p,q} \geq 0, \quad \sum_{q=1}^m T_{p,q} = a_p \quad (\forall p), \quad \sum_{p=1}^n T_{p,q} = b_q \quad (\forall q).$$

This linear program has nm variables and $n + m$ equality constraints. For dense costs, generic LP solvers (e.g., network simplex or interior-point) costs $O(n^3 + m^3)$ time and $O(n^2 + m^2)$ memory in practice, which is prohibitive at large scale [22].

Entropy-regularized OT (1-Wasserstein Distance). To accelerate computation and obtain a smooth, differentiable objective, we use the entropy-regularized formulation:

$$W_{1,\varepsilon} = \min_T \underbrace{\sum_{p=1}^n \sum_{q=1}^m C_{p,q} T_{p,q}}_{\text{OT cost}} + \varepsilon \underbrace{\sum_{p=1}^n \sum_{q=1}^m T_{p,q} \log T_{p,q}}_{\text{entropy regularization } (\varepsilon > 0)} \quad \text{s.t. } T\mathbf{1} = a, \quad T^\top \mathbf{1} = b, \quad T \geq 0. \quad (1.21)$$

By continuity we set $0 \log 0 := 0$. Smaller ε yields an objective closer to unregularized OT but usually requires more iterations.

With the entropic objective in Eq. (1.21), define the Gibbs kernel $K := \exp(-C/\varepsilon)$ elementwise. The optimal plan has the scaling form $T^* = \text{diag}(u) K \text{diag}(v)$ with $u \in \mathbb{R}_+^n$ and $v \in \mathbb{R}_+^m$, where $\text{diag}(u)$ denotes the diagonal matrix formed from vector u . Enforcing the marginals $T^* \mathbf{1} = a$ and $(T^*)^\top \mathbf{1} = b$ therefore reduces to a *matrix scaling* problem, for which the classical Sinkhorn–Knopp algorithm applies [4]. Starting from $u = \mathbf{1}$ and $v = \mathbf{1}$, we alternate row/column normalizations

$$u \leftarrow a \oslash (Kv), \quad v \leftarrow b \oslash (K^\top u), \quad (1.22)$$

where \oslash denotes element-wise division and $T = \text{diag}(u) K \text{diag}(v)$. The iteration terminates once the marginal residuals $\|T\mathbf{1} - a\|_1$ and $\|T^\top \mathbf{1} - b\|_1$ fall below a predefined

tolerance.

Each iteration costs $O(nm)$ time and $O(nm)$ memory (two dense matrix–vector multiplications plus element-wise operations) and is GPU-friendly. The regularization parameter ε governs an accuracy–speed trade-off: smaller ε reduces the entropic bias and yields a solution closer to unregularized OT, but typically worsens the conditioning of $K = \exp(-C/\varepsilon)$ and increases the number of iterations; larger ε improves conditioning and accelerates convergence at the expense of a smoother, more biased solution.

1.4 Multivariate Time-Series Model

A multivariate time series consists of multiple correlated temporal variables observed over time. Formally, it can be represented as

$$X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_T\} \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times N},$$

where T denotes the length of the observation window and N is the number of variables. The forecasting task aims to predict the next S time steps

$$Y = \{x_{T+1}, \dots, x_{T+S}\} \in \mathbb{R}^{S \times N},$$

given the historical sequence X . This is typically formulated as learning a mapping

$$f_\theta : \mathbb{R}^{T \times N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{S \times N},$$

that minimizes a loss function (e.g., mean squared error) between the predicted and ground-truth values.

Compared with channel-independent or univariate formulations [21, 29], multivariate modeling must capture both the *temporal dependencies* within each variable and the *inter-variable correlations* across different dimensions. These correlations are often nonlinear, non-stationary, and dynamically evolving, which poses additional challenges for model design and generalization [14]. Recent studies have reformulated multivariate time-series forecasting under a representation learning perspective [11, 31, 14, 8]: each variable can be treated as an individual temporal sequence embedded in a shared latent space, where cross-variable interactions are learned through parameterized transformations. This abstraction allows the model to flexibly encode temporal patterns, adapt to variable-specific dynamics, and generalize to diverse spatio-temporal systems.

Extension to Spatio-Temporal Forecasting. The multivariate time-series formulation can be naturally extended to the *spatio-temporal forecasting* setting, where each

variable corresponds to a distinct spatial location or sensor node. Let there be N nodes (sensors) distributed in space; at time step t , the observation can be expressed as

$$x_t = [x_{t,1}, x_{t,2}, \dots, x_{t,N}]^\top,$$

where $x_{t,i}$ denotes the measurement of the i -th node (sensor) at time t . Under this formulation, the multivariate structure can be naturally associated with a spatial topology (e.g., an adjacency matrix), allowing the model to automatically capture both *temporal dependencies* along the time axis and *spatial correlations* among nodes (sensors) from data.

However, many existing multivariate time-series models assume a fixed number of variables, which corresponds to a fixed number of nodes (sensors) in spatio-temporal forecasting. This assumption becomes restrictive in cross-city spatio-temporal learning, where different cities have heterogeneous spatial layouts and varying numbers of sensors. Such variability exceeds the capacity of models that require a predefined and constant variable dimension. Recent advancements in multivariate modeling, such as iTransformer [14] and SOFTS [8], have demonstrated that representing variables as flexible tokens enables handling data with different numbers of variables across datasets, thereby providing a more general and scalable modeling framework.

2

Theoretical Analysis

In this section, we provide a theoretical analysis for the PM module. Specifically, we analyze the generalization properties of the proposed method and establish conditions under which PM can provably reduce the domain adaptation risk.

2.1 Notation and Common Assumptions

We summarize the main symbols used in this section.

L_t Expected target risk (expected loss under the target population distribution).

L_s Expected source risk (expected loss under the source population distribution).

\hat{L}_s Empirical source risk computed on the source samples.

p_s Source population distribution.

p_t Target population distribution.

N_s Number of source samples used for empirical estimation.

N_t Number of target samples used for empirical estimation.

\hat{p}_s Empirical source distribution estimated from N_s samples.

\hat{p}_t Empirical target distribution estimated from N_t samples.

TV	Total variation distance between two distributions.
W_1	1-Wasserstein distance between two distributions.
g	Feature extractor mapping input x to latent representation z .
f	Regression head operating on z .
\mathcal{G}	Function class of feature extractor mapping input x to latent representation z .
\mathcal{F}	Function class of regression head operating on z .
\mathfrak{R}_{N_s}	Rademacher complexity of the hypothesis class on N_s samples.
C	A universal constant related to 1-Wasserstein distance. See Part D of appendix in [2].

We also assume that for all source–target domain pairs (x, y) drawn from the joint distribution $\mathcal{D}_{s,t}$, the following regularity conditions hold to ensure the theorem’s validity:

- (i) **Bounded loss.** The prediction loss is bounded:

$$\ell(f(z), y) = |f(z) - y| \in [0, M],$$

where $M > 0$ is a finite constant and $z = g(x)$ denotes the encoded representation of the input x .

- (ii) **Lipschitz continuity.** Assume $f : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is L -Lipschitz, i.e., there exists $L > 0$ such that

$$|f(z) - f(z')| \leq L \|z - z'\|_2 \quad \text{for all } z, z' \in \mathcal{Z}.$$

- (iii) **Bounded feature space.** The representation space $\mathcal{Z} = g(\mathcal{X})$ is bounded, i.e.

$$\text{diam}(\mathcal{Z}) = \sup_{z, z' \in \mathcal{Z}} \|z - z'\|_2 \leq R,$$

for some finite radius $R > 0$.

2.2 Theoretical Analysis for PM Module

In this section, we present two theorems together with their proofs, which provide theoretical analysis for the single-source domain and multi-source domain transfer generalization bounds of the PM module.

2.2.1 Theoretical Analysis for Single-Source Domain Transfer

Theorem 1 (Single-Source Domain Transfer Generalization Bound for PM Module). *Assume the conditions (i)–(iii) in Section 2.1 hold. With probability at least $1 - 5\delta$, we have*

$$L_t \leq \widehat{L}_s + 2M \text{TV}(p_t(y), p_s(y)) + L \left[\frac{1}{2N_s} \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} W_1(\widehat{p}_s(z | y_j^s), \widehat{p}_t(z | y_j^s)) + \frac{1}{2N_t} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} W_1(\widehat{p}_s(z | y_j^t), \widehat{p}_t(z | y_j^t)) + \beta \right] + \alpha,$$

where

$$\alpha = 2\mathfrak{R}_{N_s}(\mathcal{F} \circ \mathcal{G}) + M \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\delta)}{2N_s}}, \quad \beta = \sqrt{\ln \frac{1}{\delta}} \left(C + \frac{R}{2\sqrt{2}} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{N_s}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_t}} \right).$$

Interpretation. The bound decomposes the target risk into several interpretable components: the empirical source risk, a label distribution discrepancy term (measured by the label’s total variation distance), a label-conditioned feature discrepancy term (measured by the conditional optimal transport distance), a model complexity term (quantified by the Rademacher complexity), and additional sampling error terms.

This result implies that minimizing the conditional optimal transport distance can provably enhance transferability between the source and target domains. In our framework, this is achieved through the PM module, which performs conditional optimal transport alignment enhanced by the DVGP module. Furthermore, as more labeled target samples become available, the transfer generalization gap can be further reduced.

Proof of Theorem 1. We begin with a simple add-and-subtract decomposition of the target risk L_t :

$$L_t = L_s + (L_t - L_s) = \widehat{L}_s + \underbrace{(L_s - \widehat{L}_s)}_{\text{source generalization error}} + \underbrace{(L_t - L_s)}_{\text{domain shift}}. \quad (2.1)$$

Hence, to upper bound L_t it suffices to control the two residual terms on the right-hand side.

The source generalization term $(L_s - \widehat{L}_s)$ can be bounded by a standard uniform-convergence argument, via the Rademacher complexity of the hypothesis class together with the bounded-loss assumption.

The bound on the domain shift term $(L_t - L_s)$ is derived by decomposing the target–source risk gap into two components: a label-distribution discrepancy and a conditional feature-distribution discrepancy. The label term is controlled by the bounded loss assumption, resulting in dependence on the total variation distance between label distributions. The conditional term is bounded using the Lipschitz continuity of the loss,

which links the conditional risk difference to the conditional optimal transport distance between source and target representations. Finally, concentration arguments are applied to obtain a high-probability bound in the finite-sample setting.

To be specific, we split the argument into 3 steps.

Step 1: Bound on source generalization error. As shown in [19, Section 11.2.2], let $p \geq 1$ and assume that

$$|h(x) - y| \leq M, \quad \forall (x, y) \in \mathcal{X} \times \mathcal{Y}, \quad h \in \mathcal{H}.$$

Then, for any $\delta > 0$, with probability at least $1 - \delta$ over an i.i.d. sample $S = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^m$, each $h \in \mathcal{H}$ satisfies

$$\mathbb{E}_{(x,y) \sim \mathcal{D}} [|h(x) - y|^p] \leq \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m |h(x_i) - y_i|^p + 2p M^{p-1} \mathfrak{R}_m(\mathcal{H}) + M^p \sqrt{\frac{\ln \frac{1}{\delta}}{2m}}. \quad (2.2)$$

By setting $p = 1$, $\mathcal{D} = \mathcal{D}_s$ (source domain distribution), $m = N_s$ and $h(x) = f \circ g(x)$, we have

$$\mathbb{E}_{(x,y) \sim \mathcal{D}_s} [|f(g(x)) - y|] \leq \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} |f(g(x_i^s)) - y_i^s| + 2 \mathfrak{R}_{N_s}(\mathcal{F} \circ \mathcal{G}) + M \sqrt{\frac{\ln \frac{1}{\delta}}{2N_s}}. \quad (2.3)$$

By denoting the true source risk as

$$L_s = \mathbb{E}_{(x,y) \sim \mathcal{D}_s} [|f(g(x)) - y|]$$

and the empirical source risk as

$$\widehat{L}_s = \frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} |f(g(x_i^s)) - y_i^s|,$$

it becomes

$$L_s \leq \widehat{L}_s + 2 \mathfrak{R}_{N_s}(\mathcal{F} \circ \mathcal{G}) + M \sqrt{\frac{\ln \frac{1}{\delta}}{2N_s}}. \quad (2.4)$$

Thus the bound on source generalization error is

$$L_s - \widehat{L}_s \leq 2 \mathfrak{R}_{N_s}(\mathcal{F} \circ \mathcal{G}) + M \sqrt{\frac{\ln \frac{1}{\delta}}{2N_s}}. \quad (2.5)$$

Step 2: Bound on domain shift. By denoting the true target risk as

$$L_t = \mathbb{E}_{(x,y) \sim \mathcal{D}_t} [|f(g(x)) - y|],$$

then the source-target generalization gap can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} L_t - L_s &= \mathbb{E}_{(x,y) \sim \mathcal{D}_t} [|f(g(x)) - y|] - \mathbb{E}_{(x,y) \sim \mathcal{D}_s} [|f(g(x)) - y|] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{(z,y) \sim \mathcal{D}_t} [|f(z) - y|] - \mathbb{E}_{(z,y) \sim \mathcal{D}_s} [|f(z) - y|]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

By introducing the *conditional risks*

$$a_s(y) = \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_s(\cdot|y)} [|f(z) - y|],$$

$$a_t(y) = \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_t(\cdot|y)} [|f(z) - y|],$$

so that $L_s = \mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_s} [a_s(y)]$ and $L_t = \mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_t} [a_t(y)]$. Adding and subtracting $\mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_t} a_s(y)$ in (2.6) yields the following decomposition

$$\begin{aligned} L_t - L_s &= [\mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_t} a_s(y) - \mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_s} a_s(y)] \\ &\quad + \mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_t} [a_t(y) - a_s(y)]. \end{aligned} \quad (A)$$

$$= \int a_s(y) [p_t(y) - p_s(y)] dy \quad (A)$$

$$+ \int [a_t(y) - a_s(y)] p_t(y) dy \quad (B)$$

As MAE loss is bounded by M in our assumption, then

$$a_s(y) = \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_s(\cdot|y)} [|f(z) - y|] \leq \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_s(\cdot|y)} [M] = M.$$

So we have

$$\begin{aligned} |(A)| &\leq \int |p_t(y) - p_s(y)| |a_s(y)| dy \\ &\leq M \int |p_t(y) - p_s(y)| dy = 2M \text{TV}(p_t(y), p_s(y)), \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

where the total variation (TV) distance between the label distributions $p_t(y)$ and $p_s(y)$ is defined as

$$\text{TV}(p_t(y), p_s(y)) = \frac{1}{2} \int |p_t(y) - p_s(y)| dy. \quad (2.8)$$

Under assumption (ii), we have for all $z, z' \in \mathcal{Z}$:

$$| |f(z) - y| - |f(z') - y| | \leq |f(z) - f(z')| \leq L \|z - z'\|_2. \quad (2.9)$$

Dividing both sides by L shows that

$$\psi(z) = \frac{|f(z) - y|}{L} \quad (2.10)$$

is 1-Lipschitz:

$$|\psi(z) - \psi(z')| = \frac{1}{L} \left| |f(z) - y| - |f(z') - y| \right| \leq \|z - z'\|_2.$$

By definition of the conditional risks,

$$a_t(y) - a_s(y) = \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_t(\cdot|y)}[|f(z) - y|] - \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_s(\cdot|y)}[|f(z) - y|],$$

we can factor out L and write

$$\begin{aligned} a_t(y) - a_s(y) &= L \left[\mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_t(\cdot|y)} \psi(z) - \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_s(\cdot|y)} \psi(z) \right] \\ &\leq L \sup_{\|\phi\|_{\text{Lip}} \leq 1} \left[\mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_t(\cdot|y)} \phi(z) - \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_s(\cdot|y)} \phi(z) \right] \\ &= L W_1(p_s(z | y), p_t(z | y)). \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

where ϕ is any 1-Lipschitz function, by Kantorovich–Rubinstein duality [22, Section 6.1] (the supremum over all such functions recovers the 1-Wasserstein distance).

So we have

$$\begin{aligned} (\text{B}) &= \int [a_t(y) - a_s(y)] p_t(y) \, dy \\ &\leq L \int W_1(p_s(z | y), p_t(z | y)) p_t(y) \, dy \\ &= L \mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_t(y)} \left[W_1(p_s(z | y), p_t(z | y)) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

Under assumption (iii), the representation space has diameter $\text{diam}(\mathcal{Z}) \leq R$. Let $\mu = p_s(z | y)$ and $\nu = p_t(z | y)$. So for all y ,

$$W_1(p_s(z|y), p_t(z|y)) = \inf_{\pi \in \Pi(\mu, \nu)} \mathbb{E}_{(z, z') \sim \pi} [\|z - z'\|] \leq \sup_{z, z' \in \mathcal{Z}} \|z - z'\| \leq R. \quad (2.13)$$

Thus, if we let

$$s(z, y_j) = W_1(p_s(z | y_j), p_t(z | y_j)) \quad (j = 1, \dots, N_t),$$

Hoeffding's inequality gives, for any $\delta \in (0, 1)$, with probability at least $1 - \delta$:

$$\mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_t} [W_1(p_s(z | y), p_t(z | y))] \leq \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} s(z, y_j) + R \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\delta)}{2 N_t}}. \quad (2.14)$$

Accordingly, the term (B) admits the high-probability bound

$$(B) \leq L \mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_t} [W_1(p_s(z | y), p_t(z | y))] \leq L \left(\frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} s(z, y_j) + R \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\delta)}{2 N_t}} \right). \quad (2.15)$$

And further we have

$$\begin{aligned} L_t - L_s &= (A) + (B) \leq 2M \text{TV}(p_t(y), p_s(y)) \\ &\quad + L \left(\frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} W_1(p_s(z | y_j), p_t(z | y_j)) + R \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\delta)}{2 N_t}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.16)$$

with probability at least $1 - \delta$.

Similarly, if we choose another type of decomposition of $L_t - L_s$ different from (A) + (B):

$$\begin{aligned} L_t - L_s &= [\mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_t} a_t(y) - \mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_s} a_t(y)] \\ &\quad + \mathbb{E}_{y \sim p_s} [a_t(y) - a_s(y)]. \\ &= \int a_t(y) [p_t(y) - p_s(y)] dy \end{aligned} \quad (A')$$

$$+ \int [a_t(y) - a_s(y)] p_s(y) dy, \quad (B')$$

We can derive a bound similar to (2.16):

$$\begin{aligned} L_t - L_s &\leq 2M \text{TV}(p_t(y), p_s(y)) \\ &\quad + L \left(\frac{1}{N_s} \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} W_1(p_s(z | y_j), p_t(z | y_j)) + R \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\delta)}{2 N_s}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.17)$$

with probability at least $1 - \delta$.

By taking the average of (2.16) and (2.17), we have:

$$\begin{aligned} L_t - L_s &= (A') + (B') \leq 2M \text{TV}(p_t(y), p_s(y)) + L \left(\frac{1}{2N_s} \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} W_1(p_s(z | y_j), p_t(z | y_j)) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2N_t} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} W_1(p_s(z | y_j), p_t(z | y_j)) + \sqrt{\ln \frac{1}{\delta}} \cdot \frac{R}{2\sqrt{2}} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{N_s}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_t}} \right) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.18)$$

with probability at least $1 - 2\delta$ by union bound.

However, the 1-Wasserstein distance is still computed over the true distribution of z in (2.18), which still needs to give an estimation on the setting of limited samples. From Part D of appendix in [2]:

$$W_1(p_s(z | y_j), p_t(z | y_j)) \leq W_1(\widehat{p}_s(z | y_j), \widehat{p}_t(z | y_j)) + \sqrt{C \ln \frac{1}{\delta}} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{N_s}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_t}} \right). \quad (2.19)$$

with probability at least $1 - \delta$ and a constant C related to 1-Wasserstein distance .

Since the source and target may have different supports for y , so by putting (2.19) into (2.18) twice we get the bound on domain shift:

$$\begin{aligned} L_t - L_s \leq & 2M \text{TV}(p_t(y), p_s(y)) + L \left(\frac{1}{2N_s} \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} W_1(\widehat{p}_s(z | y_j), \widehat{p}_t(z | y_j)) \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{1}{2N_t} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} W_1(\widehat{p}_s(z | y_j), \widehat{p}_t(z | y_j)) + \sqrt{\ln \frac{1}{\delta}} \left(C + \frac{R}{2\sqrt{2}} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{N_s}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_t}} \right) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (2.20)$$

with probability at least $1 - 4\delta$ (by union bound), where C is the constant related to 1-Wasserstein distance.

Step 3: Final assembly. Combining (2.1)(2.5)(2.20) we have:

$$\begin{aligned} L_t \leq & \widehat{L}_s + 2M \text{TV}(p_t(y), p_s(y)) + \\ & L \left[\frac{1}{2N_s} \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} W_1(\widehat{p}_s(z | y_j^s), \widehat{p}_t(z | y_j^s)) + \right. \\ & \left. \frac{1}{2N_t} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} W_1(\widehat{p}_s(z | y_j^t), \widehat{p}_t(z | y_j^t)) + \beta \right] + \alpha, \end{aligned} \quad (2.21)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= 2\mathfrak{R}_{N_s}(\mathcal{F} \circ \mathcal{G}) + M \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\delta)}{2N_s}}, \\ \beta &= \sqrt{\ln \frac{1}{\delta}} \left(C + \frac{R}{2\sqrt{2}} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{N_s}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_t}} \right), \end{aligned}$$

holds with probability at least $1 - 5\delta$ (by union bound). \square

2.2.2 Theoretical Analysis for Multi-Source Domain Transfer

Theorem 2 (Multi-Source Domain Transfer Generalization Bound for PM Module). *Assume the conditions (i)–(iii) in Section 2.1 hold. Let $\{\mathcal{D}_{s,k}\}_{k=1}^K$ be K source domains*

with population distributions $p_{s,k}$ and sample sizes $N_{s,k}$, and let the target domain have population distribution p_t and N_t samples. For any source-weight vector $\boldsymbol{\pi} = (\pi_1, \dots, \pi_K)$ belonging to the $(K - 1)$ -dimensional probability simplex

$$\Delta^{K-1} := \left\{ \boldsymbol{\pi} \in \mathbb{R}^K : \pi_k \geq 0 \text{ for all } k, \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k = 1 \right\},$$

define the mixed source label marginal

$$p_s^\pi(y) := \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k p_{s,k}(y),$$

and the mixed empirical source risk

$$\widehat{L}_S^\pi := \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \widehat{L}_{s,k}, \quad \widehat{L}_{s,k} := \frac{1}{N_{s,k}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{s,k}} |f(g(x_j^{s,k})) - y_j^{s,k}|.$$

Let $\widehat{p}_{s,k}(z | y)$ and $\widehat{p}_t(z | y)$ be the empirical conditional distributions of the representations $z = g(x)$ given label y on source k and on the target, respectively. Then, for any $\delta \in (0, 1)$, with probability at least $1 - 5K\delta$, the target risk satisfies

$$L_t \leq \widehat{L}_S^\pi + 2M \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \text{TV}(p_t(y), p_{s,k}(y)) + L \left[\frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{\pi_k}{N_{s,k}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{s,k}} W_1(\widehat{p}_{s,k}(z | y_j^{s,k}), \widehat{p}_t(z | y_j^{s,k})) + \frac{1}{2N_t} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k W_1(\widehat{p}_{s,k}(z | y_j^t), \widehat{p}_t(z | y_j^t)) + \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \beta_k \right] + \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \alpha_k.$$

where

$$\alpha_k = 2\mathfrak{R}_{N_{s,k}}(\mathcal{F} \circ \mathcal{G}) + M \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\delta)}{2N_{s,k}}},$$

and

$$\beta_k = \sqrt{\ln \frac{1}{\delta}} \left(C + \frac{R}{2\sqrt{2}} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{N_{s,k}}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_t}} \right).$$

In particular, when $K = 1$ and $\pi_1 = 1$, this bound coincides with the single-source bound in Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 2. The proof lifts the single-source bound (Theorem 1) to the multi-source case in two steps. (i) Apply Theorem 1 to each source–target pair and use a union bound so all inequalities hold simultaneously. (ii) Take a convex combination of these inequalities with respect to the source weights to obtain a bound in terms of the weighted source risk and mixed label marginal, yielding Theorem 2.

Step 1: Apply the single-source bound to each source–target pair. Let

$\delta \in (0, 1)$ be given. For each source domain $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$, apply Theorem 1 to the pair $(p_{s,k}, p_t)$ with source sample size $N_{s,k}$ and target sample size N_t . This gives, for every k ,

$$L_t \leq \widehat{L}_{s,k} + 2M \text{TV}(p_t(y), p_{s,k}(y)) + L \left[\frac{1}{2N_{s,k}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{s,k}} W_1(\widehat{p}_{s,k}(z | y_j^{s,k}), \widehat{p}_t(z | y_j^{s,k})) + \frac{1}{2N_t} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} W_1(\widehat{p}_{s,k}(z | y_j^t), \widehat{p}_t(z | y_j^t)) + \beta_k \right] + \alpha_k, \quad (2.22)$$

where the two complexity terms have exactly the same form as in Theorem 1:

$$\alpha_k = 2\mathfrak{R}_{N_{s,k}}(\mathcal{F} \circ \mathcal{G}) + M \sqrt{\frac{\ln(1/\delta)}{2N_{s,k}}}, \quad \beta_k = \sqrt{\ln \frac{1}{\delta}} \left(C + \frac{R}{2\sqrt{2}} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{N_{s,k}}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_t}} \right).$$

We also apply the same confidence level δ to the target-side empirical quantities. By a union bound over the K source events and the target event, all inequalities in (2.22) hold simultaneously with probability at least $1 - 5K\delta$.

Step 2: Convex combination with respect to the source weights. Let $\boldsymbol{\pi} = (\pi_1, \dots, \pi_K)$ belong to the simplex

$$\Delta^{K-1} := \left\{ \boldsymbol{\pi} \in \mathbb{R}^K : \pi_k \geq 0 \ \forall k, \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k = 1 \right\}.$$

Multiply (2.22) by π_k and sum over $k = 1, \dots, K$. Since $\sum_k \pi_k = 1$, the left-hand side remains L_t , and we obtain

$$L_t \leq \underbrace{\sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \widehat{L}_{s,k}}_{=: \widehat{L}_S^\boldsymbol{\pi}} + 2M \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \text{TV}(p_t(y), p_{s,k}(y)) + L \left[\frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{\pi_k}{N_{s,k}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{s,k}} W_1(\widehat{p}_{s,k}(z | y_j^{s,k}), \widehat{p}_t(z | y_j^{s,k})) + \frac{1}{2N_t} \sum_{j=1}^{N_t} \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k W_1(\widehat{p}_{s,k}(z | y_j^t), \widehat{p}_t(z | y_j^t)) + \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \beta_k \right] + \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \alpha_k. \quad (2.23)$$

Thus, we obtain exactly the multi-source bound stated in the theorem, with probability at least $1 - 5K\delta$. When $K = 1$ and $\pi_1 = 1$, the result reduces to the single-source bound in Theorem 1. \square

Remark. In our PM module, all source cities (domains) are treated equally by default, with $\pi_i = 1/K$ for $i \in 1, \dots, K$ in Theorem 2. Interestingly, Theorem 2 suggests that allocating larger weights to source cities (domains) showing smaller distributional discrepancies from the target city (domain) could yield a lower expected target risk than

uniform weighting. In practice, such reweighting could be realized by adaptively estimating the domain similarity (e.g., using Wasserstein distance or MMD) and updating π during training. This insight highlights a promising direction for future work—developing a principled weighting scheme that dynamically balances source contributions to better match the target distribution.

3

Experiments

3.1 Experiment Setup

3.1.1 Datasets

Following the previous works of spatio-temporal few-shot learning [15, 10, 16, 18], we validate our framework on the task of traffic speed forecasting. Experiments are carried out on four widely adopted public benchmarks: PEMS-BAY and METR-LA [13], as well as two large-scale city datasets-Chengdu and Shenzhen [18]. Each of these collections spans several months of traffic speed observations; summary statistics are given in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Statistical details of traffic datasets.

Datasets	PEMS-BAY	METR-LA	Chengdu	Shenzhen
# of Nodes	325	207	524	627
# of Edges	2,694	1,722	1,120	4,845
Interval	5 min	5 min	10 min	10 min
# of Time Steps	52,116	34,272	17,280	17,280
Mean	61.7768	58.2749	29.0235	31.0092
Std	9.2852	13.1280	9.6620	10.9694

3.1.2 Few-shot Setting

We follow the few-shot experimental protocol in prior work [15, 10, 16]. Data from four cities is divided into source, few-shot target (for validation), and target test sets. Each city serves as the target in turn, with the other three as sources. All datasets use Z-score normalization. Following [16], the past 24 hours are used to predict the next 3 hours in our experiment, as long-range input windows benefit generalization in few-shot settings. We evaluate model performance using Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE), two standard metrics that measure the accuracy of the model predictions.

3.1.3 Baselines

We select 14 baselines that support long-range input for comparison:

- **Spatio-Temporal Few-shot Learning Methods:** STGFSL [18], TransGTR [12], GPD [34], STGP [10] and MTPB [16] are the recent representative spatio-temporal few-shot learning methods. We exclude recent TSJT [35] because its code is unavailable, preventing a fair comparison. Moreover, TSJT trains on both source cities and target few-shot data while relying on the test set for early stopping, which may introduce unintended test-set leakage.
- **Spatio-Temporal Foundation Model:** UniST [33] is a large-scale pretrained spatio-temporal Transformer model that uses learnable prompts for cross-city and cross-task adaptation.
- **Multivariate Time-Series Methods:** SOFTS [8] and iTransformer [14] are among the recent state-of-the-art models for multivariate time-series forecasting. Both models are capable of modeling inter-variable dependencies and accommodating domains with heterogeneous variable sets, thereby demonstrating their ability to automatically capture spatial relationships and adapt to cities with varying numbers of locations.
- **Domain Adaptation Methods:** We evaluate three standard feature-alignment regularizers: MMD [17], CORAL [27], and CMMD [24, 30]. Specifically, CMMD aligns the conditional distributions $P(g(x) | y)$ across domains based on the Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) metric, which is conceptually similar to our conditional optimal transport strategy. For a fair comparison, all three regularization terms are integrated into both the SOFTS and iTransformer backbones, with hyperparameters tuned via grid search.

3.1.4 Implementation

We follow the experimental setting of MTPB [16]. For consistency, Chengdu and Shenzhen (originally 10-min intervals) are interpolated to 5-min intervals, matching METR-LA and PEMS-BAY.

The results of STGFSL [18], TransGTR [12], GPD [34], and UniST [33] are taken from the comparative evaluation reported in [16]. For the training of MTPB [16] and STGP [10], we strictly follow the original settings from their respective papers. All other methods use our setup: only three days of target city data are available for validation, and the remaining three cities are used as sources, with the learning rate of 0.001 for the optimizer AdamW. During training, 9000 source–target city pairs are sampled for training (approximately 10 epochs to convergence), and domain adaptation is applied only after the first 4500 pairs to prevent it from interfering with model training in the early stages. As a result, some methods produce identical results, since their validation performance does not improve after applying domain adaptation loss. For PMME methods, additional 18000 source–target city pairs are sampled for training the RM module in the second stage training (about 20 epochs to convergence), with the base model parameters kept frozen.

In PMME, the label-aware coefficient is set to 100, placing greater emphasis on matching labels (patterns) rather than extracted features. In the second stage, the residual memory module uses a memory size of 10,000 and an embedding dimension of 128. We select the threshold τ (the minimum probability for a label to be considered shared between domains) and the scaling factor λ for the conditional optimal transport loss from $\{0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5\}$ and $\{0.01, 0.1, 1\}$, respectively. These hyperparameters are chosen by manual tuning:

- For target dataset METR-LA, we take $\tau = 0.3$ and $\lambda = 0.01$ for SOFTS, and $\tau = 0.1$ and $\lambda = 0.1$ for iTransformer.
- For target dataset PEMS-BAY, we take $\tau = 0.5$ and $\lambda = 1$ for SOFTS, and $\tau = 0.2$ and $\lambda = 0.01$ for iTransformer.
- For target dataset Chengdu, we take $\tau = 0.1$ and $\lambda = 0.1$ for SOFTS, and $\tau = 0.4$ and $\lambda = 0.01$ for iTransformer.
- For target dataset Shenzhen, we take $\tau = 0.5$ and $\lambda = 0.01$ for SOFTS, and $\tau = 0.4$ and $\lambda = 0.1$ for iTransformer.

For the domain adaptation methods (CORAL, MMD, and CMMD), we select the scaling factor λ for the regularizer from $\{0.1, 1, 10\}$, since these standard regularizers typically yield much smaller loss values than optimal transport. The optimal hyperparameter is chosen by searching over all possible values:

Table 3.2: Performance comparison of few-shot learning on METR-LA.

Model	P, C, S \rightarrow METR-LA							
	RMSE				MAE			
	10min	60min	120min	180min	10min	60min	120min	180min
STGFSL	5.80 \pm 0.54	9.13 \pm 0.42	10.87 \pm 0.27	11.78 \pm 0.15	3.93 \pm 0.94	5.91 \pm 1.13	7.28 \pm 0.80	8.03 \pm 0.58
TransGTR	5.46 \pm 0.22	9.31 \pm 0.43	10.78 \pm 0.17	11.45 \pm 0.35	3.18 \pm 0.07	5.09 \pm 0.14	6.32 \pm 0.15	7.25 \pm 0.22
GPD	5.30 \pm 0.20	8.82 \pm 0.21	10.91 \pm 0.12	11.31 \pm 0.28	3.20 \pm 0.07	4.99 \pm 0.12	6.47 \pm 0.12	6.76 \pm 0.32
STGP	5.12 \pm 0.01	8.47 \pm 0.02	9.99 \pm 0.06	10.52 \pm 0.08	2.83 \pm 0.00	4.32 \pm 0.00	5.19 \pm 0.04	5.55 \pm 0.06
MTPB	5.78 \pm 0.04	9.18 \pm 0.03	10.35 \pm 0.02	10.84 \pm 0.07	3.30 \pm 0.04	4.95 \pm 0.02	5.63 \pm 0.05	5.97 \pm 0.05
UniST	5.34 \pm 0.19	8.71 \pm 0.23	10.84 \pm 0.41	11.44 \pm 0.62	3.22 \pm 0.11	4.97 \pm 0.21	6.29 \pm 0.20	7.08 \pm 0.17
iTransformer	5.16 \pm 0.01	8.15 \pm 0.07	9.36 \pm 0.08	9.94 \pm 0.08	2.82 \pm 0.02	4.12 \pm 0.03	4.76 \pm 0.01	5.10 \pm 0.00
SOFTS	5.12 \pm 0.02	8.15 \pm 0.07	9.29 \pm 0.15	9.81 \pm 0.14	2.78 \pm 0.02	4.10 \pm 0.03	4.73 \pm 0.04	5.05 \pm 0.03
iTransformer+CORAL	5.22 \pm 0.08	8.17 \pm 0.12	9.32 \pm 0.09	9.86 \pm 0.04	2.85 \pm 0.04	4.13 \pm 0.03	4.78 \pm 0.02	5.11 \pm 0.02
iTransformer+MMD	5.22 \pm 0.08	8.17 \pm 0.12	9.32 \pm 0.09	9.86 \pm 0.04	2.85 \pm 0.04	4.13 \pm 0.03	4.78 \pm 0.02	5.11 \pm 0.02
iTransformer+CMMD	5.21 \pm 0.07	8.12 \pm 0.05	9.29 \pm 0.08	9.84 \pm 0.03	2.85 \pm 0.05	4.11 \pm 0.02	4.77 \pm 0.03	5.12 \pm 0.03
SOFTS+CORAL	5.09 \pm 0.04	8.16 \pm 0.05	9.27 \pm 0.08	9.76 \pm 0.05	2.76 \pm 0.03	4.10 \pm 0.02	4.73 \pm 0.00	5.05 \pm 0.02
SOFTS+MMD	5.09 \pm 0.04	8.18 \pm 0.07	9.29 \pm 0.09	9.79 \pm 0.10	2.75 \pm 0.03	4.10 \pm 0.01	4.72 \pm 0.02	5.05 \pm 0.01
SOFTS+CMMD	5.06 \pm 0.02	8.08 \pm 0.03	9.22 \pm 0.04	9.73 \pm 0.04	2.75 \pm 0.02	4.08 \pm 0.01	4.71 \pm 0.01	5.04 \pm 0.01
iTransformer+PMME	5.12 \pm 0.02**	8.17 \pm 0.02	9.34 \pm 0.06	9.87 \pm 0.03	2.75 \pm 0.01**	4.08 \pm 0.01*	4.74 \pm 0.02*	5.08 \pm 0.02*
SOFTS+PMME	5.05 \pm 0.02**	8.16 \pm 0.01	9.30 \pm 0.03	9.77 \pm 0.03	2.71 \pm 0.01*	4.05 \pm 0.01**	4.69 \pm 0.01**	5.02 \pm 0.01*

Remark: Identical rows indicate that the best validation checkpoint occurred before the domain adaptation regularizer was activated (after 4500 city-pair steps). * indicates statistical significance for PMME methods at $p < 0.05$, and ** at $p < 0.01$ (t-test).

Table 3.3: Performance comparison of few-shot learning on PEMS-BAY.

Model	M, C, S \rightarrow PEMS-BAY							
	RMSE				MAE			
	10min	60min	120min	180min	10min	60min	120min	180min
STGFSL	3.90 \pm 0.64	6.68 \pm 0.22	8.33 \pm 0.21	9.20 \pm 0.18	2.74 \pm 0.61	3.85 \pm 0.46	4.71 \pm 0.61	5.29 \pm 0.64
TransGTR	3.11 \pm 0.26	6.60 \pm 0.98	7.68 \pm 0.28	8.75 \pm 0.32	1.72 \pm 0.04	3.28 \pm 0.07	4.38 \pm 0.32	4.66 \pm 0.24
GPD	3.07 \pm 0.17	5.87 \pm 0.48	7.89 \pm 0.11	8.60 \pm 0.28	1.73 \pm 0.06	3.15 \pm 0.13	4.10 \pm 0.27	4.76 \pm 0.19
STGP	3.03 \pm 0.01	5.69 \pm 0.01	7.21 \pm 0.01	7.64 \pm 0.03	1.73 \pm 0.00	2.85 \pm 0.01	3.66 \pm 0.02	3.94 \pm 0.01
MTPB	3.00 \pm 0.06	6.17 \pm 0.12	7.73 \pm 0.51	8.61 \pm 0.60	1.68 \pm 0.04	3.23 \pm 0.15	4.28 \pm 0.45	4.93 \pm 0.48
UniST	3.08 \pm 0.05	5.90 \pm 0.15	7.66 \pm 0.14	8.66 \pm 0.30	1.68 \pm 0.06	3.20 \pm 0.11	4.14 \pm 0.21	4.68 \pm 0.22
iTransformer	2.89 \pm 0.04	5.34 \pm 0.12	6.23 \pm 0.12	6.69 \pm 0.05	1.49 \pm 0.01	2.47 \pm 0.05	2.86 \pm 0.05	3.17 \pm 0.06
SOFTS	2.80 \pm 0.01	5.27 \pm 0.06	6.04 \pm 0.04	6.54 \pm 0.02	1.46 \pm 0.03	2.40 \pm 0.02	2.76 \pm 0.03	3.03 \pm 0.01
iTransformer+CORAL	2.96 \pm 0.02	5.32 \pm 0.12	6.27 \pm 0.19	6.77 \pm 0.13	1.56 \pm 0.01	2.49 \pm 0.05	2.91 \pm 0.10	3.20 \pm 0.06
iTransformer+MMD	2.92 \pm 0.02	5.30 \pm 0.05	6.23 \pm 0.06	6.74 \pm 0.05	1.52 \pm 0.02	2.46 \pm 0.03	2.88 \pm 0.01	3.22 \pm 0.07
iTransformer+CMMD	2.87 \pm 0.02	5.31 \pm 0.03	6.21 \pm 0.02	6.64 \pm 0.03	1.49 \pm 0.01	2.45 \pm 0.03	2.85 \pm 0.02	3.13 \pm 0.11
SOFTS+CORAL	2.88 \pm 0.07	5.27 \pm 0.05	6.02 \pm 0.05	6.51 \pm 0.01	1.49 \pm 0.04	2.43 \pm 0.05	2.79 \pm 0.07	3.03 \pm 0.01
SOFTS+MMD	2.80 \pm 0.02	5.21 \pm 0.02	6.04 \pm 0.03	6.54 \pm 0.02	1.44 \pm 0.02	2.39 \pm 0.02	2.74 \pm 0.01	3.00 \pm 0.01
SOFTS+CMMD	2.77 \pm 0.03	5.24 \pm 0.04	6.05 \pm 0.09	6.59 \pm 0.08	1.43 \pm 0.03	2.38 \pm 0.00	2.75 \pm 0.01	3.01 \pm 0.00
iTransformer+PMME	2.74 \pm 0.01**	5.26 \pm 0.03*	6.20 \pm 0.09	6.61 \pm 0.04	1.41 \pm 0.01**	2.37 \pm 0.02**	2.79 \pm 0.03**	3.02 \pm 0.02**
SOFTS+PMME	2.70 \pm 0.01**	5.18 \pm 0.03*	6.02 \pm 0.04	6.50 \pm 0.06	1.39 \pm 0.01*	2.32 \pm 0.02**	2.70 \pm 0.01**	2.95 \pm 0.01**

Remark: Identical rows indicate that the best validation checkpoint occurred before the domain adaptation regularizer was activated (after 4500 city-pair steps). * indicates statistical significance for PMME methods at $p < 0.05$, and ** at $p < 0.01$ (t-test).

- For target dataset METR-LA, we take $\lambda = 1$ for SOFTS + CORAL, $\lambda = 1$ for SOFTS + MMD, $\lambda = 0.1$ for SOFTS + CMMD, $\lambda = 1$ for iTransformer + CORAL, $\lambda = 0.1$ for iTransformer + MMD, $\lambda = 0.1$ for iTransformer + CMMD.
- For target dataset PEMS-BAY, we take $\lambda = 10$ for SOFTS + CORAL, $\lambda = 0.1$ for SOFTS + MMD, $\lambda = 0.1$ for SOFTS + CMMD, $\lambda = 1$ for iTransformer + CORAL, $\lambda = 0.1$ for iTransformer + MMD, $\lambda = 0.1$ for iTransformer + CMMD.
- For target dataset Chengdu, we take $\lambda = 10$ for SOFTS + CORAL, $\lambda = 0.1$ for SOFTS + MMD, $\lambda = 0.1$ for SOFTS + CMMD, $\lambda = 10$ for iTransformer + CORAL,

$\lambda = 0.1$ for iTransformer + MMD, $\lambda = 0.1$ for iTransformer + CMMD.

- For target dataset Shenzhen, we take $\lambda = 10$ for SOFTS + CORAL, $\lambda = 0.1$ for SOFTS + MMD, $\lambda = 1$ for SOFTS + CMMD, $\lambda = 10$ for iTransformer + CORAL, $\lambda = 0.1$ for iTransformer + MMD, $\lambda = 0.1$ for iTransformer + CMMD.

Moreover, for MMD and CMMD, we set the RBF kernel bandwidth σ to the median of pairwise distances between samples, a common practice that adapts the kernel to the data scale and has been shown to perform well in domain adaptation [7].

3.2 Performance Comparison

The experimental results of all methods on all the 4 datasets are reported in Tables 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, and 3.5. From the tables, we summarize four key observations:

- MTPB and STGP are the current SOTA spatio-temporal few-shot learning methods, even outperforming the spatio-temporal foundation model UniST.
- Modern multivariate time-series models (iTransformer and SOFTS) consistently outperform MTPB and STGP. This highlights their superior ability to capture long-range temporal dependencies and to learn inter-node correlations directly from data, without relying on predefined graph structures, with variables correspond to nodes here.
- Incorporating standard domain adaptation regularizers (MMD, CORAL, CMMD) into base models yields no performance gains over their vanilla counterparts. When the regularization is activated after the 4500th city-pair iteration, some of these methods show no additional improvement in certain transfer learning tasks on the validation set. As a result, some of the final results remain identical, since their validation performance does not improve after applying domain adaptation loss. This indicates that standard domain adaptation methods do not always work well in this task.
- PMME consistently achieves lower prediction errors across all four datasets in most cases, outperforming competing methods when integrated with multivariate forecasting models, with most improvements being statistically significant under t-tests.

3.3 Ablation Study

To evaluate the contribution of each component in PMME, we perform ablation studies by progressively adding individual modules to the two backbone models, since some

Table 3.4: Performance comparison of few-shot learning on Chengdu.

Model	M, P, S \rightarrow Chengdu							
	RMSE				MAE			
	10min	60min	120min	180min	10min	60min	120min	180min
STGFSL	3.56 \pm 0.13	4.79 \pm 0.06	5.55 \pm 0.06	6.10 \pm 0.04	2.54 \pm 0.15	3.38 \pm 0.04	3.96 \pm 0.05	4.40 \pm 0.10
TransGTR	4.11 \pm 0.98	4.75 \pm 0.55	5.88 \pm 0.22	6.14 \pm 0.15	2.55 \pm 0.10	3.63 \pm 0.07	3.88 \pm 0.15	4.34 \pm 0.28
GPD	3.14 \pm 0.03	4.31 \pm 0.19	4.87 \pm 0.21	5.04 \pm 0.22	2.17 \pm 0.02	3.00 \pm 0.12	3.67 \pm 0.21	4.13 \pm 0.24
STGP	3.19 \pm 0.02	4.10 \pm 0.01	4.34 \pm 0.01	4.40 \pm 0.01	2.20 \pm 0.02	2.79 \pm 0.01	2.97 \pm 0.01	3.01 \pm 0.01
MTPB	3.14 \pm 0.00	4.00 \pm 0.04	4.28 \pm 0.11	4.25 \pm 0.04	2.17 \pm 0.01	2.73 \pm 0.03	2.94 \pm 0.08	2.95 \pm 0.02
UniST	3.39 \pm 0.12	4.45 \pm 0.14	4.78 \pm 0.23	4.96 \pm 0.22	2.31 \pm 0.21	3.10 \pm 0.09	3.58 \pm 0.19	3.87 \pm 0.24
iTransformer	3.11 \pm 0.01	3.81 \pm 0.02	3.97 \pm 0.04	4.04 \pm 0.03	2.12 \pm 0.02	2.53 \pm 0.01	2.63 \pm 0.03	2.69 \pm 0.02
SOFTS	3.05 \pm 0.00	3.76 \pm 0.02	3.88 \pm 0.01	3.93 \pm 0.01	2.07 \pm 0.01	2.50 \pm 0.00	2.58 \pm 0.00	2.62 \pm 0.01
iTransformer+CORAL	3.13 \pm 0.02	3.83 \pm 0.02	3.94 \pm 0.02	3.98 \pm 0.04	2.13 \pm 0.02	2.55 \pm 0.03	2.62 \pm 0.01	2.67 \pm 0.01
iTransformer+MMD	3.14 \pm 0.01	3.83 \pm 0.03	3.96 \pm 0.03	4.00 \pm 0.04	2.14 \pm 0.01	2.56 \pm 0.03	2.63 \pm 0.01	2.67 \pm 0.01
iTransformer+CMMD	3.14 \pm 0.01	3.83 \pm 0.03	3.96 \pm 0.03	4.00 \pm 0.04	2.14 \pm 0.01	2.56 \pm 0.03	2.63 \pm 0.01	2.67 \pm 0.01
SOFTS+CORAL	3.04 \pm 0.01	3.78 \pm 0.02	3.90 \pm 0.03	3.92 \pm 0.01	2.06 \pm 0.00	2.52 \pm 0.01	2.61 \pm 0.02	2.62 \pm 0.01
SOFTS+MMD	3.07 \pm 0.02	3.76 \pm 0.01	3.90 \pm 0.02	3.94 \pm 0.01	2.08 \pm 0.01	2.50 \pm 0.01	2.59 \pm 0.03	2.63 \pm 0.02
SOFTS+CMMD	3.07 \pm 0.02	3.76 \pm 0.01	3.90 \pm 0.02	3.94 \pm 0.01	2.08 \pm 0.01	2.50 \pm 0.01	2.59 \pm 0.03	2.63 \pm 0.02
iTransformer+PMME	3.06 \pm 0.01**	3.78 \pm 0.01**	3.92 \pm 0.02	3.95 \pm 0.02	2.07 \pm 0.00**	2.50 \pm 0.01**	2.59 \pm 0.01*	2.62 \pm 0.01**
SOFTS+PMME	3.03 \pm 0.00	3.74 \pm 0.01*	3.85 \pm 0.01**	3.90 \pm 0.00**	2.04 \pm 0.00**	2.47 \pm 0.00**	2.54 \pm 0.00**	2.58 \pm 0.00**

Remark: Identical rows indicate that the best validation checkpoint occurred before the domain adaptation regularizer was activated (after 4500 city-pair steps). * indicates statistical significance for PMME methods at $p < 0.05$, and ** at $p < 0.01$ (t-test).

Table 3.5: Performance comparison of few-shot learning on Shenzhen.

Model	M, P, C \rightarrow Shenzhen							
	RMSE				MAE			
	10min	60min	120min	180min	10min	60min	120min	180min
STGFSL	3.56 \pm 0.50	4.44 \pm 0.34	5.06 \pm 0.16	5.50 \pm 0.10	2.70 \pm 0.58	3.10 \pm 0.46	3.42 \pm 0.27	3.77 \pm 0.14
TransGTR	3.45 \pm 0.12	4.28 \pm 0.74	4.87 \pm 0.65	4.55 \pm 0.05	2.40 \pm 0.34	2.88 \pm 0.10	3.30 \pm 0.10	3.48 \pm 0.22
GPD	2.78 \pm 0.03	3.88 \pm 0.08	4.70 \pm 0.09	5.14 \pm 0.18	1.88 \pm 0.03	2.67 \pm 0.04	3.16 \pm 0.04	3.59 \pm 0.15
STGP	2.98 \pm 0.02	3.79 \pm 0.02	4.04 \pm 0.03	4.12 \pm 0.04	2.00 \pm 0.01	2.50 \pm 0.01	2.65 \pm 0.02	2.73 \pm 0.02
MTPB	2.77 \pm 0.03	3.65 \pm 0.01	3.91 \pm 0.05	4.03 \pm 0.03	1.87 \pm 0.02	2.36 \pm 0.01	2.49 \pm 0.01	2.60 \pm 0.06
UniST	2.89 \pm 0.07	3.85 \pm 0.10	4.56 \pm 0.18	4.45 \pm 0.11	1.99 \pm 0.05	2.70 \pm 0.07	3.19 \pm 0.06	3.40 \pm 0.14
iTransformer	2.77 \pm 0.01	3.50 \pm 0.01	3.65 \pm 0.00	3.73 \pm 0.01	1.84 \pm 0.01	2.23 \pm 0.00	2.30 \pm 0.01	2.34 \pm 0.00
SOFTS	2.73 \pm 0.02	3.49 \pm 0.01	3.64 \pm 0.01	3.71 \pm 0.01	1.80 \pm 0.01	2.21 \pm 0.01	2.30 \pm 0.01	2.34 \pm 0.01
iTransformer+CORAL	2.79 \pm 0.02	3.51 \pm 0.01	3.64 \pm 0.01	3.72 \pm 0.01	1.85 \pm 0.02	2.23 \pm 0.01	2.30 \pm 0.01	2.35 \pm 0.00
iTransformer+MMD	2.81 \pm 0.02	3.53 \pm 0.01	3.69 \pm 0.03	3.76 \pm 0.02	1.86 \pm 0.01	2.26 \pm 0.01	2.33 \pm 0.01	2.38 \pm 0.01
iTransformer+CMMD	2.81 \pm 0.02	3.53 \pm 0.01	3.69 \pm 0.03	3.76 \pm 0.02	1.86 \pm 0.01	2.26 \pm 0.01	2.33 \pm 0.01	2.38 \pm 0.01
SOFTS+CORAL	2.73 \pm 0.00	3.48 \pm 0.02	3.64 \pm 0.01	3.72 \pm 0.03	1.81 \pm 0.00	2.21 \pm 0.00	2.29 \pm 0.01	2.33 \pm 0.01
SOFTS+MMD	2.73 \pm 0.01	3.47 \pm 0.01	3.64 \pm 0.01	3.71 \pm 0.01	1.80 \pm 0.01	2.20 \pm 0.00	2.29 \pm 0.01	2.33 \pm 0.00
SOFTS+CMMD	2.73 \pm 0.01	3.48 \pm 0.00	3.64 \pm 0.00	3.72 \pm 0.01	1.80 \pm 0.01	2.21 \pm 0.01	2.30 \pm 0.01	2.33 \pm 0.01
iTransformer+PMME	2.74 \pm 0.00**	3.48 \pm 0.00**	3.63 \pm 0.00*	3.69 \pm 0.01**	1.80 \pm 0.00**	2.20 \pm 0.00**	2.28 \pm 0.00**	2.32 \pm 0.00**
SOFTS+PMME	2.71 \pm 0.01*	3.45 \pm 0.01**	3.62 \pm 0.01**	3.68 \pm 0.02*	1.78 \pm 0.00**	2.18 \pm 0.00**	2.26 \pm 0.00**	2.30 \pm 0.01**

Remark: Identical rows indicate that the best validation checkpoint occurred before the domain adaptation regularizer was activated (after 4500 city-pair steps). * indicates statistical significance for PMME methods at $p < 0.05$, and ** at $p < 0.01$ (t-test).

components are designed to function effectively only in conjunction with others, while keeping all hyperparameters fixed. As shown in Tables 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, and 3.9, **OT**, **Ycat**, and **DVGP** represent different parts of the **PM** module:

- **OT**: Applies optimal transport regularization, using uniform mass vectors when employed alone.
- **Ycat**: Concatenates the feature representation $g(x)$ with the regression label y , enabling label-aware alignment.
- **DVGP**: Employs a deep variational Gaussian process to generate adaptive mass vectors for the optimal transport step.

- **Proj**: Incorporates the gradient projection technique to mitigate conflicting optimization signals between source and target domains.
- **RM**: Applies the Residual Memory module in the second stage to correct prediction residuals on underrepresented target patterns.

Results show that vanilla OT alone may degrade performance, but adding further components generally improves accuracy, highlighting the effectiveness of each module in

Table 3.6: Ablation Study of our PMME method on METR-LA.

Model	P, C, S → METR-LA							
	RMSE				MAE			
	10min	60min	120min	180min	10min	60min	120min	180min
iTransformer	5.16 ± 0.01	8.15 ± 0.07	9.36 ± 0.08	9.94 ± 0.08	2.82 ± 0.02	4.12 ± 0.03	4.76 ± 0.01	5.10 ± 0.00
+OT	5.22 ± 0.08	8.17 ± 0.12	9.32 ± 0.09	9.86 ± 0.04	2.85 ± 0.04	4.13 ± 0.03	4.78 ± 0.02	5.11 ± 0.02
+OT+Ycat	5.12 ± 0.03	8.10 ± 0.02	9.30 ± 0.03	9.89 ± 0.03	2.77 ± 0.02	4.09 ± 0.01	4.76 ± 0.01	5.13 ± 0.02
+OT+Ycat+DVGP	5.13 ± 0.03	8.06 ± 0.02	9.24 ± 0.03	9.82 ± 0.02	2.79 ± 0.01	4.10 ± 0.02	4.75 ± 0.01	5.13 ± 0.02
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj	5.16 ± 0.02	8.17 ± 0.04	9.37 ± 0.11	9.87 ± 0.09	2.82 ± 0.04	4.13 ± 0.03	4.76 ± 0.04	5.13 ± 0.05
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj+RM	5.12 ± 0.02	8.17 ± 0.02	9.34 ± 0.06	9.87 ± 0.03	2.75 ± 0.01	4.08 ± 0.01	4.74 ± 0.02	5.08 ± 0.02
SOFTS	5.12 ± 0.02	8.15 ± 0.07	9.29 ± 0.15	9.81 ± 0.14	2.78 ± 0.02	4.10 ± 0.03	4.73 ± 0.04	5.05 ± 0.03
+OT	5.09 ± 0.01	8.12 ± 0.06	9.25 ± 0.06	9.80 ± 0.09	2.77 ± 0.02	4.08 ± 0.00	4.73 ± 0.00	5.08 ± 0.01
+OT+Ycat	5.12 ± 0.03	8.21 ± 0.09	9.34 ± 0.08	9.86 ± 0.08	2.76 ± 0.04	4.09 ± 0.04	4.73 ± 0.02	5.06 ± 0.01
+OT+Ycat+DVGP	5.08 ± 0.03	8.14 ± 0.07	9.25 ± 0.03	9.76 ± 0.02	2.74 ± 0.03	4.07 ± 0.02	4.70 ± 0.02	5.03 ± 0.01
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj	5.10 ± 0.02	8.20 ± 0.01	9.35 ± 0.05	9.81 ± 0.05	2.74 ± 0.02	4.08 ± 0.01	4.71 ± 0.02	5.03 ± 0.02
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj+RM	5.05 ± 0.02	8.16 ± 0.01	9.30 ± 0.03	9.77 ± 0.03	2.71 ± 0.01	4.05 ± 0.01	4.69 ± 0.01	5.02 ± 0.01

Table 3.7: Ablation Study of our PMME method on PEMS-BAY.

Model	M, C, S → PEMS-BAY							
	RMSE				MAE			
	10min	60min	120min	180min	10min	60min	120min	180min
iTransformer	2.89 ± 0.04	5.34 ± 0.12	6.23 ± 0.12	6.69 ± 0.05	1.49 ± 0.01	2.47 ± 0.05	2.86 ± 0.05	3.17 ± 0.06
+OT	2.96 ± 0.02	5.32 ± 0.12	6.27 ± 0.19	6.77 ± 0.13	1.56 ± 0.01	2.49 ± 0.05	2.91 ± 0.10	3.20 ± 0.06
+OT+Ycat	2.88 ± 0.02	5.29 ± 0.02	6.21 ± 0.09	6.71 ± 0.03	1.52 ± 0.02	2.43 ± 0.02	2.84 ± 0.03	3.12 ± 0.04
+OT+Ycat+DVGP	2.85 ± 0.04	5.29 ± 0.05	6.17 ± 0.10	6.66 ± 0.09	1.48 ± 0.03	2.44 ± 0.03	2.84 ± 0.04	3.09 ± 0.02
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj	2.81 ± 0.01	5.30 ± 0.04	6.27 ± 0.08	6.67 ± 0.04	1.46 ± 0.00	2.41 ± 0.02	2.84 ± 0.02	3.05 ± 0.02
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj+RM	2.74 ± 0.01	5.26 ± 0.03	6.20 ± 0.09	6.61 ± 0.04	1.41 ± 0.01	2.37 ± 0.02	2.79 ± 0.03	3.02 ± 0.02
SOFTS	2.80 ± 0.01	5.27 ± 0.06	6.04 ± 0.04	6.54 ± 0.02	1.46 ± 0.03	2.40 ± 0.02	2.76 ± 0.03	3.03 ± 0.01
+OT	2.91 ± 0.07	5.34 ± 0.12	6.16 ± 0.18	6.60 ± 0.14	1.52 ± 0.04	2.45 ± 0.05	2.83 ± 0.07	3.05 ± 0.03
+OT+Ycat	2.75 ± 0.05	5.20 ± 0.06	6.09 ± 0.05	6.62 ± 0.01	1.45 ± 0.05	2.35 ± 0.02	2.73 ± 0.02	2.99 ± 0.01
+OT+Ycat+DVGP	2.75 ± 0.05	5.21 ± 0.03	6.06 ± 0.02	6.54 ± 0.05	1.43 ± 0.02	2.38 ± 0.00	2.75 ± 0.03	2.98 ± 0.04
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj	2.72 ± 0.00	5.17 ± 0.03	6.02 ± 0.04	6.50 ± 0.04	1.41 ± 0.01	2.34 ± 0.02	2.71 ± 0.01	2.97 ± 0.01
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj+RM	2.70 ± 0.01	5.18 ± 0.03	6.02 ± 0.04	6.50 ± 0.06	1.39 ± 0.01	2.32 ± 0.02	2.70 ± 0.01	2.95 ± 0.01

Table 3.8: Ablation Study of our PMME method on Chengdu.

Model	M, P, S → Chengdu							
	RMSE				MAE			
	10min	60min	120min	180min	10min	60min	120min	180min
iTransformer	3.11 ± 0.01	3.81 ± 0.02	3.97 ± 0.04	4.04 ± 0.03	2.12 ± 0.02	2.53 ± 0.01	2.63 ± 0.03	2.69 ± 0.02
+OT	3.14 ± 0.01	3.83 ± 0.03	3.96 ± 0.03	4.00 ± 0.04	2.14 ± 0.01	2.56 ± 0.03	2.63 ± 0.01	2.67 ± 0.01
+OT+Ycat	3.11 ± 0.01	3.81 ± 0.00	3.91 ± 0.01	3.98 ± 0.02	2.12 ± 0.01	2.54 ± 0.01	2.61 ± 0.01	2.66 ± 0.01
+OT+Ycat+DVGP	3.08 ± 0.00	3.80 ± 0.02	3.94 ± 0.04	3.98 ± 0.03	2.09 ± 0.00	2.53 ± 0.02	2.61 ± 0.02	2.66 ± 0.02
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj	3.08 ± 0.00	3.80 ± 0.01	3.94 ± 0.04	4.03 ± 0.05	2.09 ± 0.00	2.52 ± 0.01	2.61 ± 0.02	2.67 ± 0.05
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj+RM	3.06 ± 0.01	3.78 ± 0.01	3.92 ± 0.02	3.95 ± 0.02	2.07 ± 0.00	2.50 ± 0.01	2.59 ± 0.01	2.62 ± 0.01
SOFTS	3.05 ± 0.00	3.76 ± 0.02	3.88 ± 0.01	3.93 ± 0.01	2.07 ± 0.01	2.50 ± 0.00	2.58 ± 0.00	2.62 ± 0.01
+OT	3.07 ± 0.02	3.76 ± 0.01	3.90 ± 0.02	3.94 ± 0.01	2.08 ± 0.01	2.50 ± 0.01	2.59 ± 0.03	2.63 ± 0.02
+OT+Ycat	3.07 ± 0.01	3.76 ± 0.02	3.90 ± 0.01	3.96 ± 0.00	2.09 ± 0.00	2.50 ± 0.02	2.60 ± 0.01	2.64 ± 0.01
+OT+Ycat+DVGP	3.06 ± 0.01	3.74 ± 0.02	3.87 ± 0.01	3.93 ± 0.01	2.09 ± 0.01	2.49 ± 0.01	2.57 ± 0.02	2.61 ± 0.01
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj	3.05 ± 0.03	3.78 ± 0.05	3.86 ± 0.01	3.90 ± 0.00	2.06 ± 0.02	2.50 ± 0.02	2.55 ± 0.00	2.60 ± 0.01
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj+RM	3.03 ± 0.00	3.74 ± 0.01	3.85 ± 0.01	3.90 ± 0.00	2.04 ± 0.00	2.47 ± 0.00	2.54 ± 0.00	2.58 ± 0.00

Table 3.9: Ablation Study of our PMME method on Shenzhen.

Model	M, P, C \rightarrow Shenzhen							
	RMSE				MAE			
	10min	60min	120min	180min	10min	60min	120min	180min
iTransformer	2.77 \pm 0.01	3.50 \pm 0.01	3.65 \pm 0.00	3.73 \pm 0.01	1.84 \pm 0.01	2.23 \pm 0.00	2.30 \pm 0.01	2.34 \pm 0.00
+OT	2.81 \pm 0.02	3.53 \pm 0.01	3.69 \pm 0.03	3.76 \pm 0.02	1.86 \pm 0.01	2.26 \pm 0.01	2.33 \pm 0.01	2.38 \pm 0.01
+OT+Ycat	2.76 \pm 0.02	3.49 \pm 0.02	3.65 \pm 0.02	3.74 \pm 0.01	1.83 \pm 0.02	2.24 \pm 0.04	2.32 \pm 0.04	2.37 \pm 0.04
+OT+Ycat+DVGP	2.75 \pm 0.01	3.50 \pm 0.01	3.65 \pm 0.01	3.72 \pm 0.02	1.82 \pm 0.01	2.22 \pm 0.00	2.29 \pm 0.00	2.33 \pm 0.01
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj	2.76 \pm 0.01	3.48 \pm 0.01	3.63 \pm 0.01	3.71 \pm 0.02	1.82 \pm 0.01	2.21 \pm 0.01	2.29 \pm 0.00	2.33 \pm 0.01
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj+RM	2.74 \pm 0.00	3.48 \pm 0.00	3.63 \pm 0.00	3.69 \pm 0.01	1.80 \pm 0.00	2.20 \pm 0.00	2.28 \pm 0.00	2.32 \pm 0.00
SOFTS	2.73 \pm 0.02	3.49 \pm 0.01	3.64 \pm 0.01	3.71 \pm 0.01	1.80 \pm 0.01	2.21 \pm 0.01	2.30 \pm 0.01	2.34 \pm 0.01
+OT	2.73 \pm 0.01	3.48 \pm 0.01	3.63 \pm 0.01	3.71 \pm 0.01	1.80 \pm 0.01	2.21 \pm 0.01	2.30 \pm 0.02	2.34 \pm 0.02
+OT+Ycat	2.74 \pm 0.01	3.48 \pm 0.01	3.64 \pm 0.01	3.71 \pm 0.00	1.80 \pm 0.00	2.20 \pm 0.00	2.29 \pm 0.01	2.33 \pm 0.01
+OT+Ycat+DVGP	2.73 \pm 0.01	3.48 \pm 0.01	3.63 \pm 0.01	3.70 \pm 0.01	1.80 \pm 0.00	2.20 \pm 0.00	2.29 \pm 0.00	2.33 \pm 0.00
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj	2.72 \pm 0.01	3.47 \pm 0.01	3.63 \pm 0.00	3.70 \pm 0.02	1.80 \pm 0.00	2.20 \pm 0.00	2.28 \pm 0.01	2.31 \pm 0.00
+OT+Ycat+DVGP+Proj+RM	2.71 \pm 0.01	3.45 \pm 0.01	3.62 \pm 0.01	3.68 \pm 0.02	1.78 \pm 0.00	2.18 \pm 0.00	2.26 \pm 0.00	2.30 \pm 0.01

PMME. However, as shown in Table 3.6, the gradient projection method slightly degrades performance on the METR-LA dataset, indicating that gradient projection may not be universally effective across all datasets. These results verify that each module contributes incrementally to PMME’s overall performance and robustness.

3.4 Hyperparameter Analysis

Figure 3.1: Impact of τ and λ on METR-LA, average RMSE and MAE on horizons {10min, 60min, 120min, 180min}.

As illustrated in Figures 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, and 3.4, we examine the effects of two key hyperparameters across the four datasets: the threshold τ , which defines the minimum probability for a pattern (label) to be considered shared between domains, and the scaling factor λ , which controls the weight of the optimal transport loss for conditional distribution alignment.

For each experiment, we fix one hyperparameter to the value used in our main setting while varying the other to isolate its individual effect. Our analysis shows that λ typically exhibits a clear optimal range, whereas τ does not, since each source city requires a different threshold for optimal alignment. An appropriate τ helps filter out dissimilar patterns and promotes accurate matching of shared ones. However, an excessively high τ may exclude genuinely shared patterns, while a too low τ may cause unrelated patterns to be aligned.

Similarly, choosing a suitable λ enables effective conditional distribution alignment without overly constraining the model’s fitting capacity. A large λ may cause over-alignment, resulting in loss of necessary information for prediction, whereas a small λ may lead to insufficient alignment of similar patterns across cities.

Figure 3.2: Impact of τ and λ on PEMS-BAY, average RMSE and MAE on horizons {10min, 60min, 120min, 180min}.

Figure 3.3: Impact of τ and λ on Chengdu, average RMSE and MAE on horizons {10min, 60min, 120min, 180min}.

Figure 3.4: Impact of τ and λ on Shenzhen, average RMSE and MAE on horizons {10min, 60min, 120min, 180min}.

3.5 Target Fine-Tuning Analysis

Table 3.10: PMME Performance With and Without Target Fine-Tuning on METR-LA.

Model	P, C, S \rightarrow METR-LA							
	RMSE				MAE			
	10min	60min	120min	180min	10min	60min	120min	180min
iTransformer+PMME (w/o FT)	5.12 \pm 0.02	8.17 \pm 0.02	9.34 \pm 0.06	9.87 \pm 0.03	2.75 \pm 0.01	4.08 \pm 0.01	4.74 \pm 0.02	5.08 \pm 0.02
iTransformer+PMME (w/ FT)	5.12 \pm 0.02	8.20 \pm 0.02	9.38 \pm 0.06	9.91 \pm 0.04	2.74 \pm 0.01	4.09 \pm 0.01	4.74 \pm 0.02	5.10 \pm 0.03
SOFTS+PMME (w/o FT)	5.05 \pm 0.02	8.16 \pm 0.01	9.30 \pm 0.03	9.77 \pm 0.03	2.71 \pm 0.01	4.05 \pm 0.01	4.69 \pm 0.01	5.02 \pm 0.01
SOFTS+PMME (w/ FT)	5.05 \pm 0.02	8.15 \pm 0.02	9.29 \pm 0.01	9.77 \pm 0.03	2.71 \pm 0.01	4.07 \pm 0.01	4.70 \pm 0.01	5.02 \pm 0.01

Table 3.11: PMME Performance With and Without Target Fine-Tuning on PEMS-BAY.

Model	M, C, S \rightarrow PEMS-BAY							
	RMSE				MAE			
	10min	60min	120min	180min	10min	60min	120min	180min
iTransformer+PMME (w/o FT)	2.74 \pm 0.01	5.26 \pm 0.03	6.20 \pm 0.09	6.61 \pm 0.04	1.41 \pm 0.01	2.37 \pm 0.02	2.79 \pm 0.03	3.02 \pm 0.02
iTransformer+PMME (w/ FT)	2.74 \pm 0.01	5.23 \pm 0.04	6.20 \pm 0.09	6.61 \pm 0.04	1.41 \pm 0.01	2.36 \pm 0.02	2.80 \pm 0.03	3.03 \pm 0.02
SOFTS+PMME (w/o FT)	2.70 \pm 0.01	5.18 \pm 0.03	6.02 \pm 0.04	6.50 \pm 0.06	1.39 \pm 0.01	2.32 \pm 0.02	2.70 \pm 0.01	2.95 \pm 0.01
SOFTS+PMME (w/ FT)	2.73 \pm 0.03	5.19 \pm 0.03	6.07 \pm 0.05	6.55 \pm 0.06	1.40 \pm 0.02	2.32 \pm 0.01	2.72 \pm 0.01	2.96 \pm 0.01

Table 3.12: PMME Performance With and Without Target Fine-Tuning on Chengdu.

Model	M, P, S \rightarrow Chengdu							
	RMSE				MAE			
	10min	60min	120min	180min	10min	60min	120min	180min
iTransformer+PMME (w/o FT)	3.06 \pm 0.01	3.78 \pm 0.01	3.92 \pm 0.02	3.95 \pm 0.02	2.07 \pm 0.00	2.50 \pm 0.01	2.59 \pm 0.01	2.62 \pm 0.01
iTransformer+PMME (w/ FT)	3.06 \pm 0.01	3.77 \pm 0.02	3.92 \pm 0.01	3.95 \pm 0.02	2.07 \pm 0.00	2.49 \pm 0.01	2.59 \pm 0.01	2.62 \pm 0.02
SOFTS+PMME (w/o FT)	3.03 \pm 0.00	3.74 \pm 0.01	3.85 \pm 0.01	3.90 \pm 0.00	2.04 \pm 0.00	2.47 \pm 0.00	2.54 \pm 0.00	2.58 \pm 0.00
SOFTS+PMME (w/ FT)	3.02 \pm 0.00	3.74 \pm 0.01	3.85 \pm 0.01	3.90 \pm 0.00	2.05 \pm 0.00	2.47 \pm 0.01	2.54 \pm 0.00	2.58 \pm 0.00

Table 3.13: PMME Performance With and Without Target Fine-Tuning on Shenzhen.

Model	M, C, S \rightarrow Shenzhen							
	RMSE				MAE			
	10min	60min	120min	180min	10min	60min	120min	180min
iTransformer+PMME (w/o FT)	2.74 \pm 0.00	3.48 \pm 0.00	3.63 \pm 0.00	3.69 \pm 0.01	1.80 \pm 0.00	2.20 \pm 0.00	2.28 \pm 0.00	2.32 \pm 0.00
iTransformer+PMME (w/ FT)	2.74 \pm 0.00	3.47 \pm 0.00	3.62 \pm 0.00	3.69 \pm 0.01	1.80 \pm 0.00	2.20 \pm 0.00	2.28 \pm 0.00	2.33 \pm 0.01
SOFTS+PMME (w/o FT)	2.71 \pm 0.01	3.45 \pm 0.01	3.62 \pm 0.01	3.68 \pm 0.02	1.78 \pm 0.00	2.18 \pm 0.00	2.26 \pm 0.00	2.30 \pm 0.01
SOFTS+PMME (w/ FT)	2.70 \pm 0.01	3.45 \pm 0.01	3.62 \pm 0.01	3.68 \pm 0.01	1.78 \pm 0.00	2.18 \pm 0.00	2.26 \pm 0.00	2.30 \pm 0.00

Prior works [10, 16] fine-tune models on few-shot target data during the final stage. To mitigate potential overfitting, we fine-tune only the final regression head while freezing all other parameters and adopt 5-fold cross-validation for early stopping. Across all four datasets, this fine-tuning strategy yields no significant change in test performance, with fluctuations within noise and no consistent gains over the non-fine-tuned baseline (Table 3.10, 3.11, 3.12 and 3.13). This suggests that simple fine-tuning brings no meaningful benefit in few-shot settings with long-range input windows, underscoring the need for more advanced and effective fine-tuning strategies.

3.6 Time Efficiency Analysis

Table 3.14: Training Time per Batch of PMME and Backbone Models on Four Datasets.

Model	METR-LA	PEMS-BAY	Chengdu	Shenzhen
iTransformer	0.18 ± 0.01 s/batch	0.22 ± 0.02 s/batch	0.23 ± 0.01 s/batch	0.24 ± 0.01 s/batch
iTransformer+PMME (Stage I)	0.35 ± 0.01 s/batch	0.40 ± 0.05 s/batch	0.52 ± 0.01 s/batch	0.55 ± 0.01 s/batch
iTransformer+PMME (Stage II)	0.10 ± 0.01 s/batch	0.12 ± 0.05 s/batch	0.14 ± 0.01 s/batch	0.14 ± 0.00 s/batch
SOFTS	0.16 ± 0.01 s/batch	0.17 ± 0.01 s/batch	0.19 ± 0.01 s/batch	0.20 ± 0.01 s/batch
SOFTS+PMME (Stage I)	0.33 ± 0.01 s/batch	0.36 ± 0.02 s/batch	0.53 ± 0.01 s/batch	0.48 ± 0.01 s/batch
SOFTS+PMME (Stage II)	0.10 ± 0.00 s/batch	0.12 ± 0.02 s/batch	0.14 ± 0.01 s/batch	0.13 ± 0.00 s/batch

Table 3.14 summarizes the average training time per batch for the backbone models and their PMME-enhanced variants across four datasets. The results indicate that the proposed PMME framework introduces a moderate computational overhead during the first-stage training, while maintaining efficiency in the second-stage residual memory learning. Specifically, integrating the Pattern Matching (PM) module approximately doubles the per-batch training time compared to the plain backbones due to the additional optimal transport and DVGP computation required for cross-city alignment. However, this cost remains acceptable considering the substantial improvement in transfer accuracy.

In contrast, the second-stage Residual Memory (RM) training is lightweight and updates quickly, adding less than 0.15 seconds per batch on average. This is because the backbone parameters are frozen, and only the memory module is updated during fine-tuning. Overall, the results demonstrate that PMME achieves a favorable balance between computational efficiency and transfer performance. The added training overhead is minor relative to the gains in cross-city generalization, making PMME both effective and practical for large-scale spatio-temporal forecasting tasks.

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